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Information And Communication Technology And The Nigerian Rules Of Evidence

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ABSTRACT

It is a fact that in Nigeria and the World over, the adoption of information and communication technology (ICT) has radically altered the channels and method of human interaction. Also, the fact that the Nigerian legal system must strive to keep up with these advancements in human interaction cannot be over emphasized. This paper seeks to examine the applicability of the Nigerian Rules of Evidence to information and communication technology (ICT) related matters, specific issues bordering on the admissibility and relevancy of evidence originating from ICT sources has been considered in this paper with a view to ascertaining the efficacy or otherwise of our existing Rules of evidence in dealing with these advancements in human interaction.

Keywords: information and communication technology, law of evidence, Evidence Act

INTRODUCTION

Evidence law, being both substantive and procedural, is the platform upon which trial proceedings is conducted to prove claims and allegations in courts through admissible evidence. The fulcrum of the law of evidence and the Evidence Act is to provide the guidelines, rules and procedures for admitting or rejecting those evidence that are not in line or fall short of the provisions of the evidence law or the Evidence Act.¹

In the few years, the use of computers in Nigeria has grown tremendously, so in present days, communication systems, financial transactions, smart card reader for election purposes etc depend on computers. The Judiciary, therefore, faces serious challenges to cope with technological development, especially as it affects the treatment of electronically generated evidence. This is so because the issue of admissibility of evidence in a court of law or tribunal is crucial to any trial whether in civil or criminal matters because it has the capacity to determine the outcome of a particular case.² However, a case may be lost or won on the strength of a particular piece of evidence that has been admitted or rejected as the case may be.

¹ Owena Bank (Nig) Plc V Punjal National Bank (2000) 5 NWLR (Pt 658) P. 635

² <http://www.theeagleonline.com.ng> Visited on 10th June, 2016

What is evidence?

The word evidence is derived from the Latin '*evident*' Meaning 'obvious'.³ Aguda is of the view that evidence arises when a court faced with the problem of the determination of a suit before it, it can solve such a problem only after making an inquiry into the relevant facts of the case as tendered before it by the parties.⁴ He goes further to define judicial evidence as the means by which the facts are proved, but excluding inferences and arguments.⁵

Evidence has also been said to be material adduced at trial to establish disputed facts.⁶ The Evidence Act, 2011, does not specifically define the word evidence, any more than simply stating that "Evidence may be given in a suit or proceeding of the existence or non-existence of every fact in issue and of such other facts as are hereafter declared to be relevant, and of no others".⁷ Section 258 of the Act defines a fact in issue to "*include any fact from which either by itself or in connection with other facts the existence, non existence, nature or extent of any right, liability or disability asserted or denied in any suit or proceeding necessarily follows*"

In line with the foregoing, it can safely be said that evidence is a testimony and/ or presentation of documents, records, objects and other related items to prove the existence or non-existence of a fact in issue or disputed facts into which a court enquires.

Applicability of ICT to the Nigerian Rules of Evidence

The very fundamental innovation introduced into our evidentiary rules by the Evidence Act, 2011 is the express provision for admissibility of statements in documents produced by computers. Under the Evidence Act, 2011⁸ there is a clear expression which provides that: "*In any proceedings a statement contained in a document produced by a computer shall be admissible as evidence of any fact stated in it of which direct oral evidence would be admissible, if it is shown that the conditions in sub-section (2) of this section are satisfied in relation to the statement and computer in question*"⁹.

The operating word "shall be admissible" means that the court or tribunal is under obligation to admit such evidence provided the four condition mentioned under the Evidence Act 2011 are met, that is to say:

- That the document containing the statement was produced by the computer during a period over which the computer was used regularly to store or process information for the purposes of any activities regularly carried on over that period, whether for profit or not, by anybody, whether corporate or not, or by any individual;
- That over that period there was regularly supplied to the computer in the ordinary course of those of those activities information of the kind from which the information so contained is derived;
- That throughout the material part of that period, the computer was operating properly or if not, that in any respect in which it was not operating properly or was out of operation during that part of that period was not such as to affect the production of the document or the accuracy of its contents; and
- That the information contained in the statement reproduces or is derived from information supplied to the computer in the ordinary course of those activities.¹⁰

Moreover, under the Evidence Act, 2011, a "document" includes the followings:

- a) Books, maps, plans, graphs, drawings, photographs and also includes any matter expressed or described upon any substance by means of letters, figures or marks or by more than one of these means, intended to be used for the purpose of recording that matter ;

³ <http://www.vocabulary.com/dictionary/evidence> visited on 10th June, 2016

⁴ Aguda, T. A., *The Law of Evidence*. 3rd Edition (Ibadan, Spectrum Law Publishing, 1989) P. 3

⁵ Ibid

⁶ Durston, G., *The Law of Evidence*, 3rd Edition (Ibadan, Spectrum Law Publishing, 1989) P.3

⁷ Section 1 Evidence Act, Cap. E. 14, LFN, 2011

⁸ Section 84 (1), Evidence Act, Cap. E. 14, LFN, 2011

⁹ Section 84 Ibid

¹⁰ Section 84 (2) (a-d) Ibid

- b) Any disc, tape, sound tract or other device in which sounds or other data (not being visual images) are embodied so as to be capable (with or without the aid of some other equipment) of being reproduced from it ;
- c) Any film, negative, tape or other device in which one or more visual images are embodied so as to be capable (with or without the aid of some other equipment) of being reproduced from it ; and
- d) Any device by means of which information is recorded, stored or retrievable including computer output.¹¹

Similarly, under the Evidence Act, 2011, there is also a clear statutory provision which says: “Entries in books of account or electronic records regularly kept in the course of business are admissible whenever they refer to a matter into which the court has to inquire, but such statements shall not alone be sufficient evidence to charge any person with liability”¹²

With the benefit of hindsight, it is crystal clear that the aforementioned section gave rise to the controversy whether computer generated evidence shall be adequate to charge any person with a legal responsibilities. See **First Bank of Nigeria PLC V Uwanda**¹³ see further the case of **Udoro V The Governor, Akwa Ibom State**.¹⁴

Relevancy and Admissibility of Evidence

Relevancy and admissibility are the foundation and backbone of the law of evidence in Nigeria.¹⁵ Section 1 of the Evidence Act 2011 states that: “*Evidence may be given in any suit or proceeding of the existence or non-existence of every fact in issue and of such other facts as are hereafter declared to be relevant and of no other*”

And the same Act defines ‘fact in issue’ as: “*any fact which either by itself or in accordance or in connection with other facts the existence, non existence, nature or extent of any right, liability or disability asserted or denied in any suit or proceeding necessarily follows*”

The foregoing means that for a piece of evidence to be admissible, it primarily must be shown that, that piece of evidence is either a relevant fact and is in issue, or in the alternative, the fact must be that which is relevant to a fact in issue. This means that the admissibility of any evidence presupposes the fact that, that evidence is relevant.

Relevancy is judged and/or gauged by the provisions of the Evidence Act and not the rules of logic or instinct.¹⁶ In **Dr. Tobi V Chief Ukpabi**¹⁷ referred to in **B.O.N V Saleh**¹⁸ as per Eso, JSC, the issue was succinctly put thus: “*admissibility should be based on relevance and not proper custody, once a matter, be it document or oral evidence is relevant, it is admissible*”

Admissibility is a rule of evidence and it is based on relevancy. In determining the admissibility of a piece of evidence, the court will not occupy itself with the question of the source of the evidence or how it was obtained;¹⁹ rather the court is bound to determine whether what is to be admitted is relevant to the issue being tried.

Thus, it is the Act that determines whether a computer or electronically generated evidence is relevant and/or admissible. Consequently, the evidence generated when a bank cashier enters into the institution’s electronic data base, the records of deposits and withdrawals made by a customer, or the records created when an ATM card user interacts with a financial institution is made insofar as it is connected with a fact

¹¹ Section 258 (1) Ibid

¹² Section 51 Ibid

¹³{2001} FWLR (Pt. 57) 1696 CA

¹⁴ {2010} 11 NWLR (Pt. 1205) 322

¹⁵ Osipitan, T., “Admissibility of Computer Printout under Nigerian Law of Evidence” (Oct. 1995) Vol.2 No.2, Lawyers’ Bi-Annual, 236 at 239

¹⁶ **Katto V CBN** {1991} 9 NWLR (Pt. 214) 126 at 145-146

¹⁷ {1984} SCNLR, 214

¹⁸ {1999} 9 NWLR (Pt. 618) 331, 344

¹⁹ See **Abubakar V Chuks** {2008} 152 LRCN 1, 17

in issue in any of the ways referred to in the Evidence Act relating to relevancy of fact, becomes a relevant fact and is therefore admissible.

The submission would be the same where a printout or a record of a transaction carried out through the instrumentality of ICT tools which contains facts that are the occasion, cause or effect, immediate or otherwise, of relevant facts, or facts in issue, or which constitute the state of things under which they happened, or which afforded an opportunity for their occurrence or transaction is sought to be tendered.²⁰

CONCLUSION

It must be mentioned here that the regulations for the admissibility of evidence, are meant to guarantee due process and fair procedure and to avoid the court being misled. There is no gainsaying the fact that the rules of evidence in Nigeria was not prepared and is still not prepared for ICT and its adoption.

Thus, it would be wrong to say that the rules and/or law of evidence in Nigeria do not recognize evidence generated and/or created with ICT. Consequently, it is submitted that it would amount to a miscarriage of justice for a court of law to refuse to consider and/or over look evidence because it was generated, created and/or stored using ICT knowledge and/or tools.

In view of the foregoing, it is submitted that any evidence of financial transactions and services whether electronically generated or created are relevant and admissible whenever there is a nexus between them and a matter before a court of law in Nigeria. Therefore, the foregoing submission is premised on the fact that admissibility or non admissibility of evidence is based on the sole consideration of whether the evidence is relevant and nothing more.

Findings

That the evidence generated and/or created through ICT tools is admissible and relevant to the matter before the court based on the provision of section 84 of the Evidence Act, 2011.

That some of the Nigerian judges are so skeptical to allow digitally generated evidence in their respective courts.

That our nation's Evidence Act needs to encapsulate some rules of evidence to information and communication technology (ICT) related matters.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the foregoing submission we recommend the following:

Nigeria shall emulate and/or adopt the method of some developed countries that are well-advanced technologically, thereby allowing the admissibility of computer generated evidence in our courts.

We also recommend that, the legislatures shall reform the law dealing with the admissibility of digitally generated evidence in Nigeria.

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²⁰ Abubakar V Chuks (2008), supra, n.7

Owena Bank (Nig.) PLC V Punjal National Bank (2000) 5 NWLR (Pt. 658) P. 635

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